

Tailoring Digital Middleware for Rural Needs: Insights from User Feedback Analysis

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Abstract. The digitalization of rural areas is essential for bridging the socio-economic gap between urban and rural communities. However, the adoption of digital technologies in rural environments faces significant barriers, including limited infrastructure, technical knowledge requirements, and user accessibility challenges. For this reason, middleware platforms aim to enhance digital infrastructure and interoperability in rural areas by providing user-friendly digital services. This paper presents an evaluation of the feedback obtained on the AURORAL middleware for rural areas to understand its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. By analyzing insights from focus groups and questionnaires with eight pilots, we aim to highlight the real-world challenges and benefits experienced by participants when interacting with the middleware. This feedback is crucial for refining such solutions to meet better the needs of diverse stakeholders, including those providing and accessing services, and ensuring its successful adoption. Moreover, the findings of this study emphasize the importance of user-centered design in overcoming digital barriers, enhancing usability and accessibility, and promoting sustainable development in rural areas, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive digital transformation.

Keywords: Rural Digitalization · Digital Middleware · User Feedback

1 Introduction

The digital divide between urban and rural areas presents significant socio-economic challenges, with rural regions often lagging behind in technological advancements and access to digital services [5]. This divide limits the potential for economic growth and innovation in rural communities, exacerbating disparities in education, healthcare, and other essential services [26]. As a result, rural areas experience fewer job opportunities and reduced access to quality healthcare and education [12]. These challenges hinder the potential for these areas to contribute to broader national and regional economic goals, including those related to sustainability and climate change mitigation [17]. Bridging this gap is crucial for fostering inclusive growth and ensuring that rural areas can fully participate in digital innovations [23].

The lack of digital infrastructure and limited access to information and communication technologies (ICT) contribute to a cycle of marginalization, where rural areas struggle to attract businesses and retain populations [7]. Additionally, digital adoption in these regions is often impeded by a lack of digital literacy and capacity among users [24], [14]. This barrier underscores the need for tools that are not only powerful and effective but also intuitive and easy to use [3]. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize the needs and preferences of end-users throughout the development process of digital tools [1]. User feedback plays a pivotal role in this approach, providing critical insights into the usability, accessibility, and functionality of digital platforms [15]. By capturing the experiences and challenges users face, developers can refine and tailor these tools to better meet the unique needs of rural communities [25], [11]. This iterative feedback process not only improves the overall user experience but also increases the likelihood of successful adoption and sustained use, ensuring that digital solutions are truly beneficial and impactful.

This paper evaluates user feedback on AURORAL’s middleware to identify and address usability issues. AURORAL³ is a digital ecosystem based on a service-oriented architecture designed to reduce the digital divide between urban and rural areas by enhancing interoperability and connectivity in rural regions. It leverages semantic technologies and the Internet of Things (IoT) to create a more connected digital environment, facilitating data exchange and service integration across various sectors, fostering dynamic ecosystems of innovation, and enabling rural areas to better engage with digital transformation [9]. AURORAL comprises several key components, including software, open APIs, and web-based interfaces for managing data exchange rules and configuring IoT infrastructures. These components enable users to participate in, configure, and engage with an ecosystem of services.

By analyzing insights from a focus group and a questionnaire conducted with participants across eight pilot sites, we aim to understand the real-world challenges and benefits experienced by users interacting with this middleware. These pilots, representing diverse rural settings, provide a comprehensive view of the platform’s usability in real-world conditions. The methodology includes structured discussions and open-ended questions to understand user experiences, technical challenges, and improvement suggestions. Through thematic analysis of this qualitative data, key areas for enhancement are highlighted, such as improving user interfaces and documentation to accommodate varying levels of digital literacy. These findings offer insights into designing digital solutions that align with the needs of rural users and support their socio-economic development. Additionally, they underscore the importance of incorporating user feedback in developing digital solutions for rural areas, promoting inclusivity and fostering sustainable growth in rural communities. The outcomes provide valuable lessons for future digital initiatives aimed at rural development.

³ <https://www.auroral.eu>

2 Related Work

The socio-economic divide between urban and rural regions, exacerbated by disparities in digital access and technology utilization, is a well-documented phenomenon. Studies by Cunha et al. [5] and Ihsaniyati et al. [13] highlight the challenges rural areas face due to the delayed adoption of digital technology, which limits their economic growth and integration into broader economic and social structures. Similarly, Hosseini et al. [12] and Wang [26] discuss how these disparities negatively affect employment, healthcare access, and educational opportunities in rural communities. This necessitates a thorough analysis of these barriers to effectively address the challenges of unequal urban and rural development. Understanding these obstacles is crucial before exploring how technological solutions can contribute to bridging the digital divide.

The concept of smart villages and the role of local populations are pivotal in overcoming these barriers. Zerrer [27] highlights that smart villages are central actors in this transformation, emphasizing the importance of engaging these communities in the digitalization process. The traditional reliance on face-to-face interactions and personal networks for service provision in rural areas underscores the need to enhance digital literacy and engagement [8]. This approach is vital for increasing the adoption and effective use of digital solutions, thereby addressing the spatial digital divide that impedes the digitalization of rural communities. Several studies have linked the lack of digital infrastructure in rural areas to ongoing socio-economic marginalization [7]. In this line, Brenes et al. [3] and Coughlin [4] argue that robust digital tools, which are user-friendly and accessible, are crucial to mitigate these issues and improve rural inclusivity.

Furthermore, a user-centered design approach is crucial in ensuring that technological solutions meet the specific needs of rural populations. This approach emphasizes the importance of user feedback, which is essential for tailoring digital tools to fit the unique contexts and requirements of users. Studies by Dopp et al. [6] and Miesenberger et al. [18] show that incorporating user insights leads to higher technology adoption rates by making solutions more intuitive and relevant. Iterative feedback loops help technology providers to refine digital products to better serve user needs [21], highlighting the role of participatory design in overcoming cultural and educational barriers [10]. Moreover, recent studies emphasize the importance of understanding and addressing the specific needs of rural areas to bridge the digital divide effectively. Stitzlein et al. [22] demonstrate that participatory design methods, which actively involve local stakeholders in the development process, ensure that digital technologies align with the cultural and practical realities of rural communities. By engaging with local communities and users and considering their unique economic and environmental contexts, digital tools become more relevant and user-friendly, ultimately boosting adoption rates and effectiveness. These insights highlight the necessity of integrating user-centered design principles with a deep understanding of local contexts to create impactful technological solutions for rural areas.

3 Procedure and Methodology

This section focuses on the methodologies and procedures for engaging with users and service developers to collect essential feedback. The evaluation aimed to identify usability issues, gather insights into user experiences, and determine areas for improvement to enhance the platform’s functionality and user-friendliness. It consisted of two main components to provide both qualitative and quantitative insights: a focus group and a questionnaire.

3.1 Focus group: gathering pilot’s feedback

The focus group was meticulously designed to delve deeply into user experiences and perceptions of the system. Its essence lies in fostering a collaborative and open environment [20]. The primary aim was to gather insights to guide the ongoing development and enhancement of the platform, ensuring it meets the current needs of its users and can adapt and evolve with their future expectations. This approach also informs the development of broader technological solutions in rural settings. A diverse group of 25 participants, including representatives from the AURORAL project’s pilot regions, alongside other project members and service developers, took part in the focus group session. This group reflected a wide range of technical backgrounds and varying levels of digital skills, with the common experience of interacting with the AURORAL middleware. Therefore, the session aimed to gather feedback on how the pilots and users integrated their use cases and services into the AURORAL ecosystem, providing valuable insights and highlighting areas for improvement within the middleware.

The session was structured to explore key thematic dimensions crucial for understanding the user experience, ranging from practical usability to more abstract and subjective experiences. The focus was on the platform’s intuitiveness, usability, and accessibility. Participants used color-coded post-its and other visual aids to represent their experiences, highlighting different aspects of the platform and pinpointing specific features needing improvement. Additionally, the focus group discussed the challenges and obstacles participants encountered. In intimate pair discussions, they explored the complexities of their interactions with the platform, providing insights valuable for immediate improvements and serving as a case study for enhancing digital interfaces in rural technology initiatives. These discussions were facilitated by digital collaborative tools for gathering feedback, creating a structured yet flexible environment for sharing detailed experiences. The session also included brainstorming activities, fostering a creative environment where participants could propose new features or enhancements.

Through varied activities and dynamics, the session facilitated a comprehensive collection of detailed information about experiences, challenges, and improvement suggestions. This approach underscores the value of user-driven insights in guiding rural digital innovation, benefiting both AURORAL and similar initiatives.

3.2 User Feedback Through Questionnaires

Following the insightful focus group session, a structured questionnaire was developed to explore the user experience further and gather additional feedback, using user-centric data to inform design and functionality improvements. This questionnaire was designed to align closely with the insights derived from the focus group, ensuring continuity in feedback collection. Its main goal is to solicit detailed, user-centric insights to guide future enhancements of the digital middleware. The questionnaire employs a mixed-method approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. Central to this approach is the use of Likert scales [16], multiple choice responses, and open questions. This variety offers respondents a range of fixed-response options, providing a quantifiable measure of their perceptions and experiences while offering a qualitative dimension to the feedback.

The initial section of the questionnaire gathers essential demographic and professional information, including the respondent's technical expertise level and role within their organization. This data is crucial for contextualizing the feedback, allowing for a nuanced understanding of how different user groups interact with such a technical tool. The questionnaire then delves into specific aspects of user experience with the AURORAL Middleware, including queries about how well the current features meet users' needs, gauged on a Likert scale, and open-ended questions about any features that are difficult to use or understand. Additionally, the stability of the middleware was another focus area, with questions about the frequency of technical issues and the types of problems encountered. This section serves to identify and address technical challenges that users face.

Furthermore, the questionnaire evaluates the effectiveness of available documentation and support mechanisms, identified as paramount aspects to enhance user experiences. In this regard, users rate the usefulness of documentation and identify the most effective means of problem resolution. Lastly, the questionnaire assesses the accessibility of the technical solution interfaces and overall user satisfaction. The comprehensive feedback collected through this questionnaire complements the one from the focus group to provide a well-rounded understanding of user needs and challenges. The outcomes from this evaluation procedure are presented in the next section.

4 Analysis and Results

This section presents the key findings derived from both the focus group and the questionnaire. The analysis first examines the focus group outcomes, offering qualitative insights into user experiences with the AURORAL platform. This highlights key themes related to usability, technical challenges, and areas for improvement. Subsequently, the questionnaire results are presented, providing quantitative data that complements the focus group insights. Together, these findings offer a comprehensive view of user satisfaction and identify specific areas needing enhancement, resulting in a holistic understanding of the user experience.

4.1 Qualitative Insights from Focus Group

As introduced, the focus group centered around discussing the usability, technical requirements, challenges, and potential improvements that may lead to further development of rural-oriented digital tools. This subsection describes the procedure used to analyze the focus group outcomes and the main conclusions drawn from the analysis. To facilitate thematic analysis, the session was first recorded, then transcribed, and finally coded into categories. The analysis of the focus group discussion concerning the AURORAL platform aimed to gather insights into user experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement. This analysis was guided by Braun and Clarke’s methodology for thematic analysis [2]. This process involved familiarization with the transcription, generating initial codes, identifying themes, reviewing themes, and defining and naming themes. Participants’ comments and interactions were scrutinized to understand their experiences and perceptions of the AURORAL platform.

The following themes were discussed and identified from the different parts of the session. To begin with, usability and intuitiveness emerged as important factors, focusing on how users perceive and interact with the platform. Then, technical Knowledge and accessibility were also highlighted, emphasizing the degree of technical expertise required to use the platform effectively. Additionally, users identified challenges in implementation, such as specific difficulties encountered, including understanding ontology. Finally, participants provided suggestions for improvement, offering recommendations for making the platform more user-friendly and accessible.

For each of them, the conducted analysis led to the following insights, grouped into the identified themes:

Usability and Intuitiveness: Participants noted that while the platform requires a solid understanding of specific technical concepts, it becomes more intuitive with familiarity. Concerns were raised about making the platform accessible and intuitive for those without an Information and Communication Technology (ICT) background. Although participants generally found the platform somewhat intuitive, they emphasized that it demands a solid technical foundation. They noted that the platform becomes more intuitive once specific concepts, like service-oriented architecture, are understood, acknowledging the initial learning curve for these technical aspects. Additionally, users agreed that solving problems often involves consulting documentation and seeking help from appropriate teams. They also emphasized the importance of participating in hands-on sessions to learn how to use the platform effectively.

Technical Knowledge and Accessibility: There is a consensus that a certain level of technical expertise, not necessarily specific to AURORAL, is necessary to effectively use the platform. A medium to high level of technical expertise was perceived as necessary. The efforts underway to make the platform more accessible to users with lower technical skills are valued, and there was an acknowledgement of the need to make the platform more accessible to users with varying technical skills. In this line, there’s an emphasis on understanding

the varying needs of different user groups, such as environmental experts and farmers, and the importance of making the platform accessible to them.

Challenges in Implementation: Some concepts, such as data representation formats and ontologies, posed specific challenges within the platform. There was a strong call for better documentation and the development of more user-friendly tools to reduce the need for a deep understanding of these complex topics. These technical challenges highlight the need for more intuitive and straightforward explanations when dealing with technological solutions that require setup and configuration, rather than detailed technical specifications. Participants' discussions on problem-solving methods indirectly highlighted ongoing challenges in implementing and integrating services. This underscores the importance of a continuous improvement approach, where user experiences directly inform the evolution of the platform's features and functionalities.

Suggestions for Improvement: In line with previous topics, suggestions for improvement focused on enhancing overall user experience and accessibility and reducing the learning curve. Following the line of the previous point, proposed improvements include the development of user-friendly tools that bypass the need for specific technical solutions such as APIs. To that end, engaging the user community for feedback and improvement suggestions is emphasized, encouraging users to share their experiences and solutions, following a user-centered approach that truly helps shape the design of user-friendly tools.

Based on Braun and Clarke's thematic methodology, the focus group analysis provided pivotal insights for developing and improving similar solutions. The feedback directly influenced the creation of new tools and resources, addressing identified user needs and challenges. The development of these new tools is a direct response to the concerns raised about usability and intuitiveness. A notable advancement from this session was the redesign of the API for interacting with the system, which was translated into a front-end UI and additional tools for handling data formats and ontologies—technical concepts that users found complex. This redesign aims to simplify user engagement with the platform's core functionalities, making it more intuitive, especially for users with limited technical expertise. This approach aligns with research emphasizing the importance of user-friendly interfaces in technology adoption [19]. It suggests that, in some cases, tools should prioritize simplicity over advanced functionality, allowing users to easily perform basic tasks and gradually explore more complex features as their proficiency grows.

Enhancing documentation is another critical area of improvement, focusing on making it more user-friendly rather than overly comprehensive, to bridge the knowledge gap for users with varying technical backgrounds. Clearer documentation is vital for facilitating user understanding and engagement with complex platforms. In this regard, it can be concluded that providing tailored educational content through documentation, specific tutorials, and sessions plays a pivotal role in integrating new users and enhancing the overall user experience. These enhancements aim to signify a shift towards a more inclusive, user-friendly platform that caters to a diverse user base with varying levels of technical expertise.

This aligns with the broader discourse on user-centered design in technology development, where user input is essential in shaping and refining digital solutions. Simpler and more straightforward documentation can often be more useful than exhaustive documentation, as it allows users to quickly find the information they need and build their confidence in using the platform.

4.2 Survey Findings and Insights

This analysis is based on data from 10 AURORAL users from the project, with pilots being the primary recipients of the survey. The respondents represent a range of roles, including decision-makers, technicians, researchers, and individuals involved in administrative work. This diversity highlights the middleware's wide application across various professional sectors. The self-identified technical expertise levels, mainly 'Intermediate' and 'Expert,' but also including "beginner", indicate that the feedback is grounded in a solid understanding of technical products, providing valuable insights into the middleware's functionality. The diversity of respondents' roles underscores the middleware's broad appeal across sectors, and their technical expertise suggests that the feedback is informed and relevant. Following the analysis of the focus group feedback, the responses are structured into several categories, which are explained below.

Feature satisfaction and accessibility: The analysis of user satisfaction with the current features of the middleware, as reflected in the responses, yields a mean satisfaction score of 7.0 (SD 1.69). This score suggests a generally positive reception among users. Delving into the distribution of responses, a range of satisfaction levels is observed. The majority, with five responses rating it at 8 and one exceptional rating of 9, reflect a high level of satisfaction. In contrast, two respondents rated their satisfaction as 6, indicating moderate positivity towards the middleware, and there were two individual ratings of 4 and 5. This diverse range of responses, spanning from moderate to high, underscores a varied user experience.

The analysis of user feedback on the accessibility and ease of use of the AURORAL Middleware interface results in a mean score of 7.3 (SD 1.56). This score denotes a generally favorable perception of the interface's accessibility among users. In this case, a significant number of users express high satisfaction, with three responses each rating the accessibility as 9 and two responses at 8. This highlights the interface's user-friendliness, which is pivotal for overall satisfaction with the system. In contrast, three respondents rated the accessibility as 6, suggesting moderate satisfaction and potentially identifying areas for improvement. Additionally, there are individual ratings of 5 and 7, which align with the expected diversity of opinions given the different user profiles and technological levels. The averaged responses for feature satisfaction and accessibility are included in Figure 1.

Technical Challenges and Feature Usability: The analysis of user feedback reveals several challenges faced by users, including issues with installation and configuration, difficulties in adhering to data standards, and the complexity of understanding technical aspects. While technically proficient users reported

Fig. 1. Distribution of responses to Likert scale questions in three categories: Feature Satisfaction, Interface Accessibility, and Overall Satisfaction of the survey.

fewer challenges, those with less expertise experienced more difficulties, highlighting the need for tools that are more accessible and user-friendly for a broader range of technical backgrounds. Feedback on newly introduced features, such as the redesigned user interface, was generally positive, with users appreciating its ease of use and improved guidance. However, not all users engaged with these features, indicating a need for increased outreach and incentives to encourage broader participation and feedback.

Issues and system stability: The questionnaire gathered information about potential technical issues and how users addressed them, providing a nuanced view of system reliability. Responses varied, with two users reporting they 'Never' experienced technical issues, seven encountering them 'Rarely,' and one encountering them 'Occasionally.' This indicates that the middleware is generally stable for most users. Notably, no users selected the option "Frequently," which suggests an overall robust and reliable performance, with most users facing minimal technical disruptions. The technical issues reported included installation problems, network connectivity issues, system crashes, and slow response times. Installation issues were the most common, indicating a need for a more streamlined and user-friendly setup process. Although system crashes and slow response times were less frequent, they highlighted areas for potential optimization to ensure consistent performance and stability. Addressing even infrequent technical issues is also crucial for maintaining smooth and efficient system usage, thereby improving the overall user experience.

Documentation and problem-solving mechanisms: User feedback on the documentation's usefulness ranges from 'Very Useful' (6 responses) to 'Extremely Useful' (2 responses), with only one respondent selecting "Somewhat Useful." The absence of responses indicating "Not Useful at All" or "Not Very Useful" suggests that the documentation is generally perceived as helpful and effective.

Useful" suggests a high level of appreciation and utility derived from the provided resources, which were iteratively improved based on previous feedback. Generally, users employ various problem-solving methods, including consulting documentation, self-troubleshooting, contacting the technical team via email, and reporting issues through available tools. The frequent use of documentation and email support highlights their effectiveness in addressing issues, particularly highlighting communication. Overall, the reliance on existing resources suggests they are accessible and helpful, reinforcing the importance of providing adequate documentation as an effective mechanism for aiding users in deploying services targeting rural areas.

Overall satisfaction: The overall satisfaction with the presented solution, based on the responses, provides a comprehensive view of user sentiment that encapsulates most of the previously evaluated aspects. Satisfaction scores range from a low of 5 to a high of 9, with a concentration of ratings at the higher end of the spectrum and an average score of 7.40 (SD 1.58). This distribution suggests that while some users experience moderate satisfaction, a significant number express high satisfaction with the middleware. Specifically, the ratings of 8 and 9 (3 responses for each) indicate a strong level of satisfaction among these users. In contrast, lower ratings, such as 5 (1 respondent) and 6 (3 respondents), though less frequent, indicate some users' reservations or unmet expectations regarding the middleware. This range of satisfaction levels highlights the importance of addressing the concerns indicated in their responses to enhance their experience and align it with those who have expressed higher satisfaction. The average responses for overall satisfaction are included in Figure 1.

5 Conclusions

This paper aimed to evaluate user feedback on digital platform solutions to identify and address usability issues. Through detailed analyses of focus group discussions and questionnaire responses regarding the AURORAL middleware—a digital solution designed to foster an ecosystem of services that empower rural development—this research provides profound insights into user experiences, highlighting technical challenges and assessing the effectiveness of newly implemented features and support mechanisms.

A key finding is the importance of making technology platforms more accessible and easier to navigate, prioritizing simplicity over comprehensiveness. Developing user-friendly interfaces that minimize the need for direct interaction with complex technical resources like APIs is essential for enhancing accessibility and usability for a broader range of users. By focusing on creating clear and straightforward solutions rather than overly complex ones, the platform can better accommodate users with varying levels of technical expertise. Additionally, fostering active communication with users, addressing their queries, refining documentation, and resolving platform issues all contribute to improved stability and accessibility.

In essence, user feedback plays a crucial role in increasing the acceptance of technology solutions, especially those targeted at rural or underrepresented areas. Feedback sessions are highly effective as they are essential for refining technology to meet users' actual needs. These sessions provide valuable insights that improve accessibility, usability, and overall satisfaction with technology platforms. This approach enhances existing features and supports the development of new ones that better align with user requirements, ensuring technology solutions are practical and responsive to a diverse user base, particularly when addressing the challenges and disparities in technology literacy associated with the digitalization of rural areas.

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References

1. Blocker, A., Datay, M.I., Mwangama, J., Malila, B.: Development of a telemedicine virtual clinic system for remote, rural, and underserved areas using user-centered design methods. *Digital Health* **10**, 20552076241256752 (2024)
2. Boyatzis, R.E.: Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development. sage (1998)
3. Brenes, J.A., López, G., Ferrández-Pastor, F.J., Marín-Raventós, G.: Usability assessment of a greenhouse context-aware alert system for small-scale farmers. *Frontiers in Computer Science* **6**, 1412913 (2024)
4. Coughlin, J.: Accessible health: An evidenced based approach to improve user experience and clinical sustainability within rural healthcare (2021)
5. Cunha, C.R., Gomes, J.P., Fernandes, J., Morais, E.P.: Building smart rural regions: Challenges and opportunities. In: *World Conference on Information Systems and Technologies*. pp. 579–589. Springer (2020)
6. Dopp, A.R., Parisi, K.E., Munson, S.A., Lyon, A.R.: Aligning implementation and user-centered design strategies to enhance the impact of health services: results from a concept mapping study. *Implementation Science Communications* **1**, 1–13 (2020)
7. Ferrari, A., Bacco, M., Gaber, K., Jedlitschka, A., Hess, S., Kaipainen, J., Koltsida, P., Toli, E., Brunori, G.: Drivers, barriers and impacts of digitalisation in rural areas from the viewpoint of experts. *Information and Software Technology* **145**, 106816 (2022)
8. Gabrielli, S., Forbes, P., Jylhä, A., Wells, S., Sirén, M., Hemminki, S., Nurmi, P., Maimone, R., Masthoff, J., Jacucci, G.: Design challenges in motivating change for sustainable urban mobility. *Computers in Human Behavior* **41**, 416–423 (2014)
9. Gómez-Carmona, O., Buján-Carballal, D., Casado-Mansilla, D., López-de Ipiña, D., Cano-Benito, J., Cimmino, A., Poveda-Villalón, M., García-Castro, R., Almela-Miralles, J., Apostolidis, D., et al.: Mind the gap: The auroral ecosystem for the digital transformation of smart communities and rural areas. *Technology in Society* **74**, 102304 (2023)

10. Harrington, C., Erete, S., Piper, A.M.: Deconstructing community-based collaborative design: Towards more equitable participatory design engagements. *Proceedings of the ACM on human-computer interaction* **3**(CSCW), 1–25 (2019)
11. Hodge, H., Carson, D., Carson, D., Newman, L., Garrett, J.: Using internet technologies in rural communities to access services: The views of older people and service providers. *Journal of Rural Studies* **54**, 469–478 (2017)
12. Hosseini, S., Frank, L., Fridgen, G., Heger, S.: Do not forget about smart towns: How to bring customized digital innovation to rural areas. *Business & Information Systems Engineering* **60**, 243–257 (2018)
13. Ihsaniyati, H., Sarwoprasodjo, S., Muljono, P., Gandasari, D.: Understanding the impact and driver of digital divide to support rural development policy: a review. In: *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*. vol. 1362, p. 012016. IOP Publishing (2024)
14. Kreslins, K., Ikse, M.R., Dreijers, G., Vasiljeva, T.: Digital literacy, digital culture and digitalization in europe. *Journal of Internet and e-Business Studies* (2022)
15. Lazar, J., Goldstein, D.F., Taylor, A.: *Ensuring digital accessibility through process and policy*. Morgan kaufmann (2015)
16. Likert, R.: A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of psychology* (1932)
17. Lishchuk, E.N., Chistiakova, O.A., Boronina, E.S., Churikova, A.A., Kapelyuk, Z.A.: Rural labor market and digitalization: New challenges and opportunities. *Frontier Information Technology and Systems Research in Cooperative Economics* pp. 159–164 (2020)
18. Miesenberger, K., Edler, C., Dirks, S., Bühler, C., Heumader, P.: User centered design and user participation in inclusive r&d: Introduction to the special thematic session. In: *Computers Helping People with Special Needs: 17th International Conference, ICCHP 2020, Lecco, Italy, September 9–11, 2020, Proceedings, Part I* 17. pp. 3–9. Springer (2020)
19. Mlekus, L., Bentler, D., Paruzel, A., Kato-Beiderwieden, A.L., Maier, G.W.: How to raise technology acceptance: user experience characteristics as technology-inherent determinants. *Gruppe. Interaktion. Organisation. Zeitschrift für Angewandte Organisationspsychologie (GIO)* **51**(3), 273–283 (2020)
20. Morgan, D.L.: Focus groups. *Annual review of sociology* **22**(1), 129–152 (1996)
21. Olsen, D.: *The lean product playbook: How to innovate with minimum viable products and rapid customer feedback*. John Wiley & Sons (2015)
22. Stitzlein, C., Fielke, S., Fleming, A., Jakku, E., Mooij, M.: Participatory design of digital agriculture technologies: Bridging gaps between science and practice. *Rural Extension and Innovation Systems Journal* **16**(1), 14–23 (2020)
23. Stojanova, S., Cvar, N., Verhovnik, J., Božić, N., Trilar, J., Kos, A., Stojmenova Duh, E.: Rural digital innovation hubs as a paradigm for sustainable business models in europe’s rural areas. *Sustainability* **14**(21), 14620 (2022)
24. Vassilakopoulou, P., Hustad, E.: Bridging digital divides: A literature review and research agenda for information systems research. *Information Systems Frontiers* **25**(3), 955–969 (2023)
25. Vitale Brovarone, E., Cotella, G.: Improving rural accessibility: A multilayer approach. *Sustainability* **12**(7) (2020), <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/7/2876>
26. Wang, Z.: The impact of the digital economy on the rural-urban income gap—moderating effects based on the level of technology market development. *Open Journal of Social Sciences* **12**(4), 335–352 (2024)
27. Zerrer, N., Sept, A.: Smart villagers as actors of digital social innovation in rural areas. *Urban Planning* **5**(4), 78–88 (2020)